

THE CONCEPT, CHARACTERISTICS AND ESSENCE OF THE STATE

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Abstract. *There are various theories about the concept and essence of the state are covered. The origin, supporters and main ideas of each theory are shown. This topic is the basis for understanding political and legal concepts. It will cover how relevant and complex the essence of the state is, its role in the modern world, effective public administration, and the well-being of society.*

Keywords: *state, concept, law, system, theory, state symbols, state border, administrative-territorial unit, population, citizen, sovereignty, management, power.*

The state is an entity that forms the basis of the political system. It performs important functions and various tasks for society. The state embodies the rights and freedoms of citizens. The state appears as a complex and diverse phenomenon and is interpreted differently in different periods. The state has its own sovereignty, that is, to control its territory, population and citizens and to carry out its activities without any external pressure in its domestic and foreign policy is one of its main tasks.

There are the following generalized approaches to defining the concept of the state:

-state (in the general sense) is a political organization that exercises supreme power in a certain area, has a special administrative apparatus, represents the interests of all socio-political groups of society, unites and coordinates them;

-state (in the legal sense) is a political organization that exercises public power in a certain area, establishes generally binding norms and has sovereignty.

The state has a border territory, that is, water, land and air resources, to exercise its power. The state can govern its territory by dividing it into administrative-territorial units.

The state has legislative, executive and judicial powers. They implement the system of public administration, introduce laws and regulations to which citizens are subject, and exercise control over it. This ensures the stability of the state.

States have such forms of government as monarchy and republic. This affects the legal status of the state and the system of governance. The characteristics of the state mean the social and political differences of the state from other states. The main features of states are expressed in the following.

- The population is united in a certain territory. The state must have a strictly defined border territory. People living here are citizens of the state. The state exercises its power in this area. The state has the right to defend its territory from external enemies. The relevant laws of the state are valid only in its border territory, and the laws of other states do not apply to this territory.

- The presence of a special management structure. The state has a complex mechanism for implementing its goals and objectives. This mechanism leads to the emergence of civil servants. The mass of the state apparatus is such that the state apparatus is relevant for the whole society. The main task of socio-political power is to serve society. These apparatuses include the legislative, executive, judicial power, law enforcement agencies, the apparatus of control of the

armed forces and penitentiary institutions. The state apparatus has the absolute right to use state coercion.

- The presence of a legal system. Without law, there will be no state. The legal system is necessary for the state to be able to carry out its activities on a legal basis. The law ensures the legitimacy of relations between the state and society and regulates the work of the state apparatus.

- Introduction of taxes. The implementation of state activities requires material needs. All residents living in the territory of the state pay a mandatory tax. Only the state has the right to collect taxes from the population. With the help of state duties, material and financial resources are formed that are necessary for state activities. They finance the activities of state bodies and ensure the implementation of the economy, environmental protection, education, health care and other areas.

- The presence of sovereignty. The state has its own sovereignty, under which the state has the ability to independently manage the domestic and foreign policy of its territory, exercise state power throughout the country, make decisions that are binding on the population, and also apply coercive measures within the framework of the law.

It is fact that understanding the essence of the state means understanding the logic, internal nature, origin, purpose and content of the state. The essence of the state is the sum of its main characteristics and internal relations. The main tasks and goals of the state are shown. They are influenced in order to regulate and develop the order of governance of state power, public relations. The essence of the state can be viewed in two ways. Firstly, public administration can be carried out for the benefit of society. In the second case, it can be done in the interests of social groups or individuals. There are different theories depending on the origin of the state, its nature, goals and paths of development. This is a complex social phenomenon; it is associated with the power of the state and the class groups under the control of power. This is the objective side. From the subjective side, this is associated with theories created by various scientists from an ideological and philosophical point of view.

It can be seen that theories about the state can be divided into four groups:

- About the nature of the state;
- About the goals and tasks of the state;
- About the means and methods of state activity;
- theories about the prospects and paths of further development of the state.

There are different scientists have expressed different opinions about the nature of the state in their works.

The theories about the nature of the state include the following:

Elite theory. This theory was developed again in the early 20th century (works by V. Pareto and G. Mosca) and in the mid-20th century (H. Lassuel, D. Sartori and T. Day). The main idea of this theory is that the masses cannot exercise control over the state, so it is proposed that it be governed by representatives of the upper classes. Representatives of the elite differ from the people in various ways (origin, education, class character). Representatives of the elite are regularly replenished from the people. This theory also has its drawbacks. In this case, the participation of the people in governing the state is excluded and the class nature of power is completely denied. But there are also positive aspects of the theory. It is assumed that representatives of the elite, that is, representatives of a limited circle - deputies, governors and employees of the state court, serve for the benefit of society and representatives of social groups.

Technocratic theory. This theory was created in the 20s of our centuries and became widespread in the 60-70s of the century. The supporters of this theory are T. Veblen, D. Barnheim, G. Simon and D. Bell. In their opinion, specialists, managers and administrators should manage the masses. Specialists can provide the necessary means for the development and interests of society. They help to reveal management from the scientific side. At present, the ideas of this theory are used not only to determine the essence of the state, but also for theories in other areas.

The theory of pluralistic democracy. This theory also appeared in the 20th century. The exponents of the theory are G. Laski, M. Duveyrier, R. Darindorf and R. Dahl. In this theory, he represents the views of both social democrats and liberals. His idea means that in modern society, classes have essentially disappeared, and power has thus freed itself from its class nature. Society consists of a set of social associations (strata) of people that arise according to various criteria - age, profession, place of residence, sphere of interests, etc. Thus, both old people and young people and athletes can unite in social associations. They could put pressure on the state power and interfere. In addition, they have their "share" in the management of public associations at any time. The positive aspect of this theory is that it represents the idea of modern democratic states.

The theory of the "welfare state". Among the theories, special attention should be paid to this theory. This theory arose after the Second World War and opposes the previously existing doctrine of non-interference of the state in public life. This theory was widely covered in the works of D. Myrdal, A. Sigu, K. Boulding and V. Munallar. It is proposed that those at the top carry out their activities taking into account the interests of the people. Human dignity and honor are placed at the center of the state, that is, they care about their interests.

The positive side of this theory is that human dignity and honor are placed at the center of the state and the interests of the people are taken into account.

The theory of the rule of law. This theory is now widespread. Today it is the most relevant and progressive. It contradicts the above principle, and it is expected that it will be implemented in all spheres of public life by legal means. This is the most relevant and advanced theory in our time. Supporters of this theory have described it in the true sense. If we consider its positive sides, then, first of all, it is the democratization of society, the complete elimination of arbitrariness, violence and lawlessness in public administration. The theory is not without negative sides, the disadvantage is that some tasks are not performed on paper due to the socio-economic situation in society.

Technocratic theory of the state. This theory arose in the 20s of the 20th century and became widespread in the 60-70s. Supporters of this theory are T. Veblen, D. Barnheim, G. Simon, D. Bell. In their opinion, the development of technology affects the development of the country. This is due to major advances in the development and use of radio electronics. According to the theory, methods have a direct impact on government. For example, polls and referendums can be conducted among the population using radio and television technologies. And computers make it possible to find fair and optimal solutions that do not depend on the will of individuals.

Convergence theory. One of the theories predicting the future of the state is the convergence theory. The theory arose in the 50-60s of the 20th century. Its supporters are D. Galbraith, R. Aron, P. Sorkin. At the present stage of human development, there is an interaction between two systems: in the West, the USA, England, etc., with the former Soviet Union and other camps. At the same time, they learn from each other, study organizational aspects, converge on each other in forms of activity, and so on. According to the theory's supporters, over time, mutual

differences will disappear and a single type of state will emerge, that is, "post-industrial states" - "welfare" states. It is necessary to recognize the ability of the theory's authors to see the future, since many theories are still used today.

Historical-materialistic theory. This theory also has its place. It analyzes many aspects of the existence and development of the state enough. The theory is based on materialism and the theory of class groups.

Its supporters are K. Marx and F. Engels. Theoretically, the state is a weapon of economic and political power of the ruling class. According to the theory's authors, for the socialist type of state the goal is to create a communist society and, ultimately, abolish the state.

The concept and essence of the state were considered multifaceted and diverse.

This is a very difficult task. The state specifically approaches the study of this task which is inextricably linked with its historical economy, social and spiritual life, training and education using existing and new scientific achievements. The essence and concept of the state have not yet found their full expression. They just tried to express it through different theories. In this article, I also wanted to contribute to the coverage of this topical issue as this is the first step of a lawyer. This topic is very important, because the mission, purpose and functions of each state constitute the essence of the state related to this work, it is also necessary to reveal the current problem and its intended to explain its essence theoretically.

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